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WEB-BASED LEARNING IN PERIODS OF CRISIS: REFLECTIONS ON THE IMPACT OF COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Education systems and its actors are generally responding to quarantine and large-scale shutdown (partial) of cities with a sudden shift to Web-Based Learning. However, given that a pandemic of this nature and scale is novel, there is a knowledge gap as to how teachers and learners should respond to the shift, and what the likely impact and the key considerations should be. This study aims to extrapolate and theorize from the existing knowledgebase about the use of Web-Based Learning, as well as from an expert and practitioner wisdom and experience, to offer high-level guidance for policymakers and education system actors that are forced to make decisions in fast-moving and very challenging circumstances with little guidance or relevant experience. It is an early attempt at theorizing the impact of the pandemic on two key actors (Learners and Teachers) and one interface (Content), all across eight dimensions of learning. The analysis is based on Khan's (2001) dimension of Web-Based Learning and Anderson's (2011) Model of Online Learning. Overall, we posit based on experience and practice, that the pandemic has delivered severe shocks to both the demand and supply side of Web-Based Learning, with Learners, Teachers, and Content all significantly affected. While we hypothesize a general drop in the quality of teaching and learning in the short run, we expect the opposite to be the case in the long run, when the demand and supply side self-correct, albeit guided by strong government and market institutions.

KEYWORDS

Web-Based Learning, COVID-19, Learners

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DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

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ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer eural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the verage absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using– ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

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CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR IRIS RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Iris is a powerful tool for reliable human identification. It has the potential to identify individuals with a high degree of assurance. Extracting good features is the most significant step in the iris recognition system. In the past, different features have been used to implement iris recognition system. Most of them are depend on hand-crafted features designed by biometrics specialists. Due to the success of deep learning in computer vision problems, the features learned by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) have gained much attention to be applied for iris recognition system. In this paper, we evaluate the extracted learned features from a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (Alex-Net Model) followed by a multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm to perform classification. The performance of the proposed system is investigated when extracting features from the segmented iris image and from the normalized iris image. The proposed iris recognition system is tested on four public datasets IITD, iris databases CASIAIris-V1, CASIA-Iris-thousand and, CASIA-Iris- V3 Interval. The system achieved excellent results with the very high accuracy rate.

KEYWORDS

Biometrics, Iris, Recognition, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Feature extraction (FE).

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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

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ENSEMBLE LEARNING MODEL FOR SCREENING AUTISM IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurological condition associated with communication, repetitive, and social challenges. ASD screening is the process of detecting potential autistic traits in individuals using tests conducted by a medical professional, a caregiver, or a parent. These tests often contain large numbers of items to be covered by the user and they generate a score based on scoring functions designed by psychologists and behavioural scientists. Potential technologies that may improve the reliability and accuracy of ASD tests are Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. This paper presents a new framework for ASD screening based on Ensembles Learning called Ensemble Classification for Autism Screening (ECAS). ECAS employs a powerful learning method that considers constructing multiple classifiers from historical cases and controls and then utilizes these classifiers to predict autistic traits in test instances. ECAS performance has been measured on a real dataset related to cases and controls of children and using different Machine Learning techniques. The results revealed that ECAS was able to generate better classifiers from the children dataset than the other Machine Learning methods considered in regard to levels of sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Neural Network, Autism Screening, Classification, Ensemble Learners, Predictive Models, Machine Learning

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DATA WAREHOUSE AND BIG DATA INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

Big Data triggered furthered an influx of research and prospective on concepts and processes pertaining previously to the Data Warehouse field. Some conclude that Data Warehouse as such will disappear; others present Big Data as the natural Data Warehouse evolution (perhaps without identifying a clear division between the two); and finally, some others pose a future of convergence, partially exploring the possible integration of both. In this paper, we revise the underlying technological features of Big Data and Data Warehouse, highlighting their differences and areas of convergence. Even when some differences exist, both technologies could (and should) be integrated because they both aim at the same purpose: data exploration and decision making support. We explore some convergence strategies, based on the common elements in both technologies. We present a revision of the state-of-the-art in integration proposals from the point of view of the purpose, methodology, architecture and underlying technology, highlighting the common elements that support both technologies that may serve as a starting point for full integration and we propose a proposal of integration between the two technologies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data, Data Warehouse, Integration, Hadoop, NoSql, MapReduce, 7V's, 3C's, M&G

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